

SPEECH PROFICIENCY IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS: A COGNITIVE PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract. *This aerticle highlights the unique ways that primary school pupils develop their speech competence in the circumstances of the fulfillment of the cognitive approach. The study discovered that the cognitive approach to language instruction helps primary school pupils develop their speaking competence. With this method, students learn how to intentionally create expressions for certain real-world scenarios. Speech competence has been shown to be an essential human attribute. It is demonstrated by the ability and willingness to use language and linguistic regularities for the construction and comprehension of speech utterances that serve a communicative purpose. We used the Oxford Cambridge 2000 software, the modified "KOC-22" technique, particular competence pedagogy standards, and indicators from Bloom's taxonomy's "Application" category to evaluate the degree of speech competence formation. Research indicates that gaining mastery over cognitive processes facilitates an individual's ability to work freely with information while learning knowledge. It is established that the text depicts speaking proficiency. The following exercise kinds are proven to be effective in the text work: research, associative, and analytical. It has been demonstrated that the cognitive approach is founded on the ideas of cognitive psychology, implying a dependence on the concept of awareness in the process of primary school children' development of speech competence. By focusing the teaching process on communicative tasks, this method guarantees that students have the appropriate degree of speech competency.*

Keywords: *primary school kids, cognitive skills, speech competency, communication objective, and cognitive approach Speech abilities and structural elements of speech activity.*

Introduction

Current trends in school language instruction suggest that the practical aspect of learning a mother tongue should be strengthened and that work on language theory should be prioritized above kids' speech development. In light of this, teaching children

to speak English effectively is an important part of the primary school language curriculum. It also helps pupils develop their intellectual culture and their spirituality. Ensuring the appropriate degree of verbal competence in students is a crucial prerequisite for effective socialization, and this strategy fulfills that need. This may be accomplished via creating novel methods and transforming language learning tools. It was discovered from observations of the English language classes and discussions with instructors and students that elementary school pupils do not adhere to the standards of the current English literary language while speaking orally or in writing. Students frequently create writings with the same lines, assuming stylistic errors, and showing a lack of awareness of the significance of a strong speech culture in communicating.

The educational works of Ushinsky, K., Sukhomlinsky, V., and Stelmakhovich, M., as well as language studies by Batsevich, F., Ermolenko, S., Kononenko, V., Kochergan, M., Selivanova, O., and Serazhim, K., serve as the foundation for the cognitive methodology. The principles of cognitive linguistics, which "views language not as "a system in itself and for itself" (F. de Saussure's phrase), but in connection with the person without whom the emergence and functioning of this system would be impossible," form the theoretical basis of cognitive methodology (Kochergan, 2003). Language functioning is considered a type of cognitive activity in cognitive linguistics. While analyzing language phenomena, the mechanisms and structures of human awareness are examined. The idea that language serves as a type of object representation that is mirrored in human psyche is at the heart of cognitive linguistics. According to scientists, frames are parts of the concept system, and this makes them a crucial notion for the cognitive methodology (Kochergan, 2003).

Diverse viewpoints exist on the definition of speech activity content. We agree with Leont'ev, O. and Zimnya, I. and describe speech skills as an individual's capacity to actualize the orientation, planning, execution, and control that make up a speech action.

In the philosophy of speech, orientation is crucial. Scholars delineate many facets (or topics) of speech action orientation: Targeting the recipient of speech while taking into account their features and capabilities; message orientation; language targeting as an objective messaging system; personal orientation or assessment by the speaker of the subject matter's significance; orientation or assessment of the degree of adequacy of the chosen linguistic means to solve the communicative problem (Hrona, 2017).

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